

STUDIES IN SESQUITERPENES. PART III. SYNTHESSES OF HOMO-CADALENES

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1-Methyl-6-ethyl-4-isopropyl- and 1-ethyl-6-methyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene have been synthesised.

In the previous part of this series (Sukh Dev, this *Journal*, 1948, 26, 69) it was reported that in connection with our investigations on the sesquiterpenes of the cadinene group it had become necessary to synthesise the then unknown methylcadalenes and the 1-methyl-6-ethyl-4-isopropyl- and 1-ethyl-6-methyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene. The syntheses of the methylcadalenes were reported there.

In a sesquiterpene of the cadinene type, when an ethylenic linkage is present as a semi-cyclic double bond, the employment of Ruzicka and Sternbach's method for the location of a double bond (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1940, 22, 124; cf. Campbell and Soffer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 417; Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*) may give rise to a homo-cadalene, thus :

Similarly, a primary alcohol will ultimately give rise to such a hydrocarbon.

With this end in view, 1-methyl-6-ethyl-4-isopropyl- and 1-ethyl-6-methyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene have been synthesised and their syntheses are reported in the present paper.

1-Ethyl-6-methyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (VII).— β -(*p*-Tolyl)propionic acid (I) is prepared by the action of succinic anhydride on toluene in nitrobenzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (cf. Barnett and Sanders, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 434). Its ethyl ester (II) is treated with ethyl magnesium bromide, when γ -(*p*-tolyl)- γ -ethylvinylacetic acid (III) is obtained in a good yield. The acid is reduced with hydroiodic acid and red phosphorus giving γ -(*p*-tolyl)- γ -ethylbutyric acid (IV). This substance has been prepared previously by Brunner and Grof (*Monatsh*, 1934, 64, 28). Their synthesis starts from 4-methylpropionophenone and is a lengthy one involving eight operations, whereas the present scheme gives much better overall yields and employs only four steps.

The acid is next cyclised with anhydrous aluminium chloride using the technique recommended by Sukh Dev and Guha (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 38; also Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*) for the ring-closure of compounds of similar structure. The tetralone (V) is obtained in a yield of 91%. Brunner and Grof (*loc. cit.*) obtained a yield of 74.6% based on the weight of pure acid chloride using anhydrous aluminium chloride. The same authors have also employed the sulphuric acid method and prepared the ketone in 61.6% yield. By the action of magnesium isopropyl bromide on 7-methyl-4-ethyltetralone-1 an unstable carbinol (VI) is obtained, which is dehydrated with 90% formic acid and then dehydrogenated with selenium to give the required homo-cadalene (VII).

1-Methyl-6-ethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (XV).— 5-Methyl-8-isopropyltetralone-1 (IX) is prepared by the cyclisation of γ -(*p*-cymyl-2)-butyric acid (VIII) (Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*). The ketone is condensed with ethyl oxalate in the presence of sodium ethoxide yielding ethyl 1-keto-5-methyl-8-isopropyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2-glyoxalate (X) (cf. Bachmann, Cole and Wilds, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 831; Bachmann and Thomas, *ibid.*, 1941, 63, 599; Bachmann and Wendler, *ibid.*, 1946, 68, 2583). The crude glyoxalate is decomposed using the procedure of Bachmann, Cole and

Wilds (*loc. cit.*) Ethyl-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-methyl-8-isopropyl-2-naphthoate (XI), thus obtained, is converted into the sodium salt and treated with ethyl bromide giving (XII) (*cf.* Kloetzel and Close, *J. Org. Chem.* 1946, **11**, 396).

The hydrolysis of such β -keto-esters has been carried out both by acids and alkalis (Titley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2578; Campbell and Soffer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 423; Bachmann, Cole and Wilds, *ibid.*, 1940, **62**, 832; Kloetzel, *ibid.*, 1940, **62**, 1711; Kloetzel and Close, *loc. cit.*). Titley (*loc. cit.*) reported that 2-methyl-2-carboethoxy-tetralone-1 on alkaline hydrolysis gave a mixture of 2-methyltetralone-1 and γ -o-carboxypnenyl- α -methylbutyric acid, whereas on hydrolysis with 20% sulphuric acid the tetralone was obtained in a quantitative yield. For our compound (XII) we selected the acid hydrolysis with 20% sulphuric acid, but even after refluxing for 15 hours, the ester was isolated unchanged. It was decided not to submit this β -keto-ester, which is so resistant to hydrolysis, to a prolonged treatment with hot alkali to avoid ring fission. Hence the keto-ester was subjected to Clemmensen reduction (Martin's modification) for 36 hours; ethyl 2-ethyl-5-methyl-8-isopropyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-2-naphthoate (XIII) was obtained in an excellent yield. Curiously enough, the ester grouping remained intact. Though an ester grouping on a quaternary carbon atom is eliminated on selenium dehydrogenation (Ruzicka and Meyer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, **5**, 581; Bardhan and Sengupta, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2520, 2798), the compound is hydrolysed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide. The acid (XIV) is isolated in a 'good yield which on

dehydrogenation with selenium gives the required 1-methyl-6-ethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene, the carboxyl group being eliminated during the reaction (cf. Diels and Karstens, *Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 2323; Darzens and Levy, *Compt. rend.*, 1934, **199**, 1131; 1935, **201**, 730; 1936, **202**, 427).

The melting points of the derivatives of these two hydrocarbons together with those of the methylcadalene derivatives are tabulated below :

TABLE I

Hydrocarbon.	B. p.	Picrate, m. p.	Styphnate, m. p.	T. N. B. compd., m. p.	T. N. T. compd., m. p.
Cadalene	—	—	—	—	—
2-Methyl-*	—	143-44°	170-71°	168-69°	—
3-Methyl-	126°-130°/2 mm.	162-63°	—	165°	—
5-Methyl-	132°/1.5 mm. 140°-145°/3 mm.	102.5-103.5°	130-31°	160-61°	87-88°
7-Methyl-*	—	122-23°	—	—	—
8-Methyl-	144°-147°/3 mm.	108-8.5°	—	118-18.5°	—
1-Ethyl-6-methyl- 4-isopropyl- naphthalene	134°-140°/2 mm.	—	—	-92°	—
1-Methyl-6-ethyl- 4-isopropyl- naphthalene	126°-127°/1 mm.	—	—	85.5-86.5°	—

* Campeli and Soffer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 417.

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Ethyl-6-methyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (VII)

β -(*p*-Toluyyl)-propionic Acid (I).—Succinic anhydride (30.0 g., 1 mol.) was condensed with toluene (30.6 g., 1.1 mol.) in dry nitrobenzene (150 c. c.) in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (89.1 g., 2.2 moles.). The details as given for the preparation of β -(*p*-cymoyl)- α -methylpropionic acid (Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*) were followed. Yield of the crude product, m. p. 121-24°, was quantitative. The crude product was dissolved in 3 parts of dry benzene and one part of petrol (b. p. 60°-80°) was added and the product was allowed to crystallise during several hours when it was obtained as colourless lustrous plates, m. p. 129-30°, yield 52 g. (90%). Barnett and Sanders (*loc. cit.*) give the m. p. as 129°.

Ethyl β -(*p*-Toluyyl)-propionate (II).—The acid (45 g.), alcohol (95%, 135 c. c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (6 c. c.) were refluxed for 7 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The ester crystallised out slowly, when it was filtered off. The crude product was carefully crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless, long needles, m. p. 42-43.5°, yield 47 g. (91%). Rupe and Steinbach (*Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 584) report the m. p. as 42-43°.

γ -(*p*-Toluyyl)- γ -ethylvinylacetic Acid (III).—A Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium, (2.2 g., 0.085 M), ethyl bromide (8 c. c., 0.1 M) and dry ether (35 c. c.). Ethyl β -(*p*-toluyyl)-propionate (11 g., 0.05 M) was dissolved in dry ether (75 c. c.) and the

inversé Grignard reaction was carried out by following the details as given for the preparation of γ -(*p*-tolyl)- γ -dimethylvinylacetic acid (Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*). The crude product was obtained as a thick reddish yellow oil in 75% yield.

Sometimes, in such reactions, if due to some reason the neutral fraction forms a considerable part of the reaction product, the β -aroyl propionic acid (present as the ester) may be separated from the $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated acid (present as the lactone or the ester) by the following method :

The crude neutral fraction is hydrolysed with alcoholic alkali (3-4 hrs.), most of the alcohol is then distilled off and the product diluted with water and extracted with ether to remove any neutral portion. The alkaline solution is clarified with norit and acidified with hydrochloric acid (Congo red); the product (solid or oil) is separated and digested with dilute hydrochloric (1: 1) on the water-bath for 2 hours. This treatment converts unsaturated acid into the lactone, whereas the keto-acid remains unaffected. The product is then taken up in ether and separated into acid and neutral fractions with sodium carbonate solution. The acid part will consist chiefly of β -aroyl propionic acid, while the neutral fraction will contain the lactone of the corresponding $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated acid, which can be submitted to hydroiodic acid reduction as such. The method has been used successfully.

γ -(*p*-Tolyl)- γ -ethylbutyric Acid (IV).—The crude unsaturated acid (21.0 g.), hydriodic acid (*d* 1.7, 105 g.) and red phosphorus (14 g.) were refluxed in an oil-bath at 130°-140° for 24 hours and worked up in the usual manner. The product was purified by distillation in vacuum. The acid was obtained as a colourless, viscous liquid, b. p. 158°/1 mm. in a yield of 66.6% (14 g.). Brunner and Grof (*loc. cit.*) report b. p. as 189°/13 mm.

4-Ethyl-7-methyltetralone-1 (V).— γ -(*p*-Tolyl)- γ -ethylbutyric acid (12 g., 1 mol.) in dry benzene (25 c. c.) was converted into the acid chloride by PCl_5 (13.5 g., 1.1 mol., covered with 25 c. c. of dry benzene) in the usual manner and the acid chloride without being purified was cyclised by anhydrous aluminium chloride (8.5 g., 1.1 mol.). The details as given for the cyclisation of γ -(*p*-cymyl-2)- α -methylbutyric acid (Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*) were followed. The reaction proper was complete in about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The product was purified by distillation in vacuum and obtained as a colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 130°-131°/1 mm., yield 10 g. (91%). Brunner and Grof. (*loc. cit.*) give the b. p. as 159°/11 mm. (Found: C, 82.30; H, 8.41. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires C, 82.97; H, 8.51 per cent).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from alcohol as colourless, small plates, m. p. 162-63° Brunner and Grof (*loc. cit.*) record 156° as the m. p.

1-Ethyl-6-methyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (VII).—*iso*Propyl magnesium bromide (prepared from magnesium 1.9 g., *iso*propyl bromide, 8 c. c. and dry ether, 50 c. c.) was reacted with the above tetralone (9 g. in 45 c. c. of dry ether) in the same way as described under 1: 3: 6-trimethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*).

The crude carbinol (10 g.), which was obtained as a viscous yellow liquid, was dehydrated with 90% formic acid (20 c. c.) by heating on a water-bath for 3 hours. The product was worked up as usual and fractionated in vacuum, when 6.0 g. (55%) of a colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 122°-130°/1 mm. were obtained.

The hydrocarbon was dehydrogenated with selenium (3 g.) in a potassium nitrate-sodium nitrite bath. The reaction started at 300° and was quite brisk. The heating was carried out at 310° for 24 hours when the evolution of hydrogen selenide had practically stopped. The product was isolated in the usual manner and purified by repeated distillations over sodium. The required naphthalene was obtained as a colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 134°-140°/2 mm. in 60% yield (3.6 g.). (Found: C, 92.53, 92.36; H, 8.76, 8.97. C₁₆H₂₀ requires C, 90.56, H, 9.43 per cent.)

The T. N. B. Compound.—The hydrocarbon (0.5 g.) was added to a hot solution of 0.5 g. of T. N. B. in 10 c. c. of alcohol and allowed to crystallise slowly. The product was once crystallised from 80% acetic acid and again from alcohol till the m. p. could not be raised further. It was obtained from alcohol as bright yellow needles, m. p. 92°.

1-Methyl-6-ethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (XV)

5-Methyl-8-isopropyl-tetralone-1 (IX) was prepared by the cyclisation of γ -(*p*-cymyl-2)-butyric acid, obtained by the Clemmensen reduction (Martin's modification) of β -(*p*-cymoyl-2)-propionic acid, which was synthesised from *p*-cymene and succinic anhydride in the presence of aluminium chloride. Details for these have been given under the synthesis of apo-cadalene (Sukh Dev and Guha, *loc. cit.*).

Ethyl 1-Keto-5-methyl-8-isopropyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydronaphthalene-2-glyoxalate (X).—Such compounds have been prepared by the condensation of cyclic ketones with oxalic esters in the presence of sodium ethoxide or sodium methoxide. Bachmann *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) have mostly used dimethyl oxalate and have employed sodium methoxide as the condensing agent. The reactions have been carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen. This condensation, however, was conducted as follows:

Dry sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium (3.45 g., 0.15 *M*) and absolute alcohol (60 c. c.), followed by removal of excess alcohol in vacuum at 100°, was suspended in 80 c. c. of dry benzene with swirling. The suspension was cooled in ice-water mixture and a solution of tetralone (15 g., 0.075 *M*) and diethyl oxalate (21.9 g., 0.15 *M*) in 30 c. c. of dry benzene was added with swirling and cooling. The mixture was swirled in the ice-bath for some time till practically all the sodium ethoxide had disappeared and a clear brownish yellow solution was obtained. The reaction mixture was kept at the room temperature (24°) for 6 hours (CaCl₂-sodalime guard tube) and was then poured on to ice. 5% Potassium hydroxide solution (50 c. c.) was added, and shaken well and the aqueous layer was separated. The benzene layer was extracted twice with 2% aqueous potash and the alkaline extracts were mixed and acidified with hydrochloric acid. An oil separated which was taken up in ether and the solution was dried (MgSO₄) and the solvent removed, when 22 g. (98%) of a dark, slightly viscous oil were left.

Ethyl 1-Keto-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydro-5-methyl-8-isopropyl-2-naphthoate (XI).—The crude glyoxalate (22 g.) and fine, soft glass powder (10 g.) were heated together in an oil-bath at 160°-170° with occasional stirring till all the carbon monoxide had been evolved (2 hrs.). The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with a little ether and the product decanted off from the glass powder. The solvent was removed and the product was distilled in vacuum, when the keto-ester was obtained as a colourless, viscous liquid,

b. p. 170° - $172^{\circ}/1$ mm., yield 15 g. (75% overall yield based on the weight of the tetralone employed). (Found: C, 75.32; H, 8.04. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 74.45; H, 8.03 per cent).

The product gives an intense green coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. With concentrated sulphuric acid a deep yellow colour is obtained. A solution of bromine in chloroform is also decolourised.

Ethyl 1-Keto-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydro-5-methyl-2-ethyl-8-isopropyl-2-naphthoate (XII).—For the alkylation of β -keto-esters of a similar structure, some workers have used one mole of sodium for one mole of the ester (e. g. Titley, *loc. cit.*), whereas others (Bachmann *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 832; 1941, **63**, 598; Kloetzel, *loc. cit.*; Kloetzel and Close, *loc. cit.*) have employed 4 moles of sodium for one mole of the keto-ester and have used the alkyl halide in large excess. These latter workers have obtained the alkylated products in very good yields. For our reaction, we have used 1.5 mole of sodium, but the alkylation was not complete, as some 5-methyl-8-isopropyltetralone-1 was isolated on hydrolysis. Hence, it will be profitable to use the method employed by Bachmann and co-workers. Kloetzel and Close (*loc. cit.*) during the ethylation of 2-carbomethoxy-1-tetralone found that ethyl bromide gave erratic results, whereas ethyl iodide worked smoothly. However, for our ethylation, we have employed ethyl bromide.

Sodium (1.8 g., 0.075 *M*) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (40 c. c.) in a dry reflux apparatus carrying a calcium chloride-sodalime guard tube. The solution was cooled and the ester (13.7 g., 0.05 *M*) dissolved in dry benzene (40 c. c.), was added. The mixture was refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, cooled and ethyl bromide (10.9 g., 0.1 *M*) introduced. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 hours and it was then refluxed for 45 minutes and left overnight. A lot of sodium bromide had separated out. The product was cooled, just neutralised with acetic acid and the solvents were removed by distillation, the last traces being removed in vacuum at 100° .

It was attempted to hydrolyse the crude ethylated product: To the residue containing the crude alkylated β -ketonic ester, 20% sulphuric acid (100 c. c.) and glacial acetic acid (10 c. c.) were added. The mixture was refluxed in an oil-bath at 130° - 140° for 15 hours and was then worked up in the usual manner. The product was fractionated in vacuum. The first fraction of b. p. 165° - $170^{\circ}/10$ mm. (yield 3.0 g.) was identified to be 5-methyl-8-isopropyltetralone-1, by its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m. p. 198.5 - 99.5° . (mixed m. p. with an authentic sample). The rest of the product was distilled in high vacuum (2nd fraction), when the distillate crystallised out. This was recrystallised from alcohol as colourless, stout, well-developed prisms, m. p. 69.5 - 70.5° , yield 7 g. The product neither gave a coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride nor a 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. (Found: C, 74.69, 74.71; H, 8.45, 8.46. $C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 8.6 per cent).

Ethyl 1 : 2 : 3 : 4-Tetrahydro-5-methyl-2-ethyl-8-isopropyl-2-naphthoate (XIII).—Zinc amalgam was prepared from zinc wool (15 g.), mercuric chloride (1.5 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.8 c. c.) and water (22 c. c.). Water, etc. were decanted off the amalgamated zinc and water (12 c. c.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (27 c. c.), toluene (15 c. c.) and the keto-ester (5 g.) were added in the order indicated. A few drops of glacial acetic acid were added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 36

hours in an oil-bath at 120°-140°. After every 6 hours, 10 c. c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid were being added. The product was worked up in the usual manner and distilled in vacuum as colourless, slightly viscous liquid, b. p. 164°-168°/5 mm., yield 4 g. (89.5%). (Found : C, 79.11 ; H, 9.59. $C_{11}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 79.16 ; H, 9.72 per cent).

1-Methyl-6-ethyl-4-isopropyl-naphthalene (XV).—The ester (4.0 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide (3.6 g. of alkali in 30 c. c. of alcohol) for 32 hours. The product was cooled, diluted with water and once extracted with ether to remove any neutral substance and then acidified (Congo red) with dilute hydrochloric acid. An oil separated which solidified on standing overnight. Yield of the crude product of m. p. 97-98° was 3.6 g. (97.3%).

The crude acid (3.5 g.) and selenium (5 g.) were heated together in a potassium nitrate-sodium nitrite bath at 300°-330° for 48 hours. The product was worked up in the usual manner and purified by distillation over sodium as colourless, mobile liquid, b. p. 126°-127°/1 mm., yield 50%. (Found : C, 90.69 ; H, 9.19. $C_{18}H_{26}$ requires C, 90.56 H, 9.43 per cent).

The *trinitrobenzene compound* was prepared by adding 0.5 g. of the hydrocarbon to T. N. B. (0.5 g.) in boiling alcohol (10 c. c.). The crystals which separated were recrystallised to a constant m. p. from alcohol. The product separated as bright, canary yellow needles, m. p. 85.5-86.5°. Mixed m. p. with the T. N. B. compound of (VII), (m. p. 92°) was 75-77° with previous shrinkage.

These two hydrocarbons (VII and XV) described in this paper yield derivatives which are quite soluble in alcohol as compared to those of the methylcadalenes. The picrates are much more soluble than the T. N. B. compounds and hence are not recommended for characterisation purposes.

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